

Article title: **Maternal anxiety and prenatal support predict pregnancy length and infant characteristics at birth during the pandemic**

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ABSTRACT

According to the theoretical prediction of the smoke detector principle, heightened anxiety as a personality trait could lead to better survival and reproductive success in unpredictable environments. Yet published studies suggest that maternal anxiety negatively affects gestation and birth outcomes, which may lead to decreased reproductive success. To resolve this conundrum, we studied the association between maternal anxiety and birth outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. Data collected from 1080 expectant mothers from the Corona Mums Project included maternal anxiety trait (STAI X2), perceived emotional support (PES), duration of gestation, and infant parameters at birth taken from hospital health records. After adjusting for covariates, multiple regression models showed that STAI X2 positively predicted infant birth weight ($\beta=0.07$, $p=0.023$) and length ($\beta=0.08$, $p=0.010$). PES positively predicted only birth

weight ($\beta=0.06$, $p=0.048$). Neither of these factors was significantly related to duration of gestation, although the association with PES was of borderline significance ($\beta=0.06$, $p=0.053$). The results suggest that maternal increased ability to detect threats, indicated by her anxiety trait during the unpredictable conditions of COVID-19, was associated with better infant characteristics at birth. This may improve infant survival and maternal reproductive success, implying that increased anxiety trait could be adaptive during environmental threats.

Keywords: anxiety trait, pregnancy outcome, smoke detector principle, behavioral immunity, COVID-19

Lay summary

During the COVID-19 pandemic, improved threat detection and maternal social support may have led to better infant outcomes. Maternal anxiety and social support were found to be mainly linked to birth weight, with threat detection affecting maternal reproductive success and infant characteristics, potentially leading to higher future survival rates.

Introduction

The impact of state anxiety during pregnancy has been extensively researched to understand its potential influence on pregnancy outcomes. Overall, anxiety defined as a temporal state of unease, fear, or worry has been found to be associated with negative effects on infant and maternal health [1]. In particular, most of the published work has suggested that a high anxiety state during pregnancy may be associated with an increased risk of preterm birth (delivery before 37 weeks of gestation) [2] and delivering a baby with low birth weight [3]. Maternal anxiety has also been studied in the context of child developmental outcomes [4]. High levels of maternal anxiety are strongly linked to an increased risk of behavioral and emotional problems in children [5,6]. Additionally, maternal anxiety during pregnancy contributes to pregnancy complications such as gestational hypertension and diabetes [7,8] and may play some role in the development of perinatal depression, disrupting the mother's ability to bond with the baby and engage in caregiving [9].

Although numerous clinical studies focus on the negative effects of increased maternal anxiety, an approach rooted in the evolutionary origins of this emotion may offer more nuanced insights into its function [10]. The notion that anxiety evolved as an adaptive defense mechanism in specific environmental challenges allows prediction about its possible positive role for

individual survival in specific ecological conditions of increased threat. According to *smoke detector principle* (SDP), anxiety serves as a protective response against health hazards or threats to survival and reproduction. By analogy to smoke alarm that give false alarms in safe environments, anxiety can be unnecessary and harmful, particularly for hypersensitive individuals. However, in detrimental conditions, the unresponsiveness to detected danger could be catastrophic. Hypersensitivity, then, becomes an asset, and previously “false reactions” protect individuals from health hazards that have gone from *potential* to *actual*. It's important to note that environmental conditions will interact with defense reactions and setting a lower threat detection threshold in an environment with many threats can be beneficial [11,12].

Anxiety trait, understood as a stable personality tendency to respond with worries to various life situations [13], will determine this threshold for threat detection and thus affect the perceived state. Individuals with a higher anxiety trait would be characterized by a lower threshold, e.g., easier detection of environmental threats and, what follows, better threat avoidance. On the contrary, lower levels of anxiety trait may be associated with increased risk to an individual's health and survival in risky environments. Still, there is limited evidence for this in humans due to the generally stable and non-threatening environments in many regions of the contemporary world [14]. In the context of the pandemic and vulnerability to pathogens, anxiety trait might also be understood as one of the mechanisms involved in the behavioral immune system, which, together with the physiological immune response, protects against infections [15]. Anxiety, interpreted as a defense response, favors individual survival and reproduction and decreases mortality risk when environmental hazards are high [10].

The recent pandemic represented a period of increased environmental threat, with nearly 350 million cases [16] and more than 6 million deaths from COVID-19 infection worldwide [17]. Unsurprisingly, it also took its toll on the psychological well-being of the population, mainly in the form of anxiety disorders and depression [18]. Theoretical predictions emerging from the SDP find their partial confirmation in epidemiological studies conducted during the recent pandemic. Studies reported increased anxiety in pregnant and lactating women during the recent outbreak [19,20]. Nevertheless, the negative effects of the pandemic on pregnancy and birth is not entirely clear. Despite a large study of over 150,000 deliveries in the US showing an increased risk of maternal gestational hypertension and diabetes, there was no observed effect of the pandemic on the rate of stillbirth. Unexpectedly, a decreased risk of spontaneous preterm labor was even observed [21]. Similarly, a large study in China based on nearly twenty thousand births during the pandemic found no effect on the rate of preterm births, but a decrease in birth weight [22]. A smaller study from Austria based on nearly 7,000 deliveries found a decreased

risk of very low gestational age and significantly higher infant birth weight compared to the pre-lockdown period [23]. Finally, a recent systematic review demonstrated a significant increase in birth weight and a decrease in the number of cases of very low birth weight during the pandemic when compared to pre-pandemic period based on results from nearly two million neonates [24]. The findings strongly suggest that while pregnant women experienced heightened anxiety during the pandemic, it did not have significant adverse effects on newborns' birth parameters. In fact, increased anxiety in expectant mothers may have positively influenced offspring survival rates.

The effect of anxiety on maternal well-being and child development is significantly influenced by genetics, postnatal caregiving, and the environment [25]. It has been established that social support, particularly emotional, effectively reduces anxiety and stress during pregnancy and postpartum [26]. Correspondingly, our previous study demonstrated a lower risk of depression and anxiety in pregnant women who participated in on-site antenatal classes during pandemics compared to those women who attended online courses or did not participate in birthing schools [27]. Such classes offer support not only as a form of professional education but also as a form of peer support from other co-participating prospective mothers. We also found that higher maternal social support is associated with a lower risk of postnatal depression [28] and better breast milk immune properties [29]. Additionally, the amount of social support, the size of the social network, and participation in specific communities were all positively related to infant size at birth and negatively to the risk of low birth weight [30–32].

The COVID-19 pandemic brought a significant psychological burden to pregnant mothers' well-being by increasing feelings of stress and anxiety [20], simultaneously limiting the possibility of accessing social support due to lockdowns and restrictions. The consequences of this burden on infant and child development remain to be quantified. To achieve this, we aimed to examine the association between maternal anxiety during pregnancy and infant gestational age and size at birth. We also extended our analysis to include the impact of social support as an important covariant affecting pregnancy course and birth outcome. Following the logic of SDP, we hypothesized that higher anxiety as a trait might be associated with better pregnancy outcomes during the threatening period of the pandemic. Thus, we expected that women with higher anxiety trait (i.e., a lower threshold of threat detection) would have longer gestation and give birth to children with higher weight and length. We also hypothesized that higher social support would be associated with better pregnancy outcomes. Notably, higher emotional support could be related to higher gestational age, higher body mass, and length at birth.

Methods

Study group

The initial study group included 1774 women who participated in the longitudinal Corona Mums Project, which aimed to explore the effect of psychosocial effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal well-being and pregnancy outcomes (<https://osf.io/5cveq/>). Women were recruited between May 2020 and March 2021 via advertisements published on social media (pregnancy and breastfeeding-related groups), radio broadcasts, newspapers, and parenthood-related magazines. At the time of the recruitment, women had to be pregnant and not suffer from severe pregnancy complications. Complete data were gathered for 1137 women and their infants from singleton pregnancies. In addition, women who smoked cigarettes (n=37) and gave birth to preterm and very preterm infants (gestational age ≤ 36 weeks; n=20) were excluded from the analysis since both preterm delivery and maternal smoking have significant effects on pregnancy outcomes. Since only a few women declared drinking alcohol in relatively small quantities during pregnancy, we decided not to exclude them from the study sample. The final study group consisted of 1080 mothers who gave birth to a single healthy infant. At the time of data collection, 131 women (12.1%) were in their first trimester, 392 (36.3%) in the second trimester, and 557 (51.6%) in the third trimester of pregnancy.

All participants of the project provided the informed consent and were informed of their right to resign from the survey at any given point without any negative repercussions. The study protocol was approved by the Bioethics Committee of Jagiellonian University (no: 1072.6120.359.2020). The database is publicly available from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16263884>.

Maternal demographics, pregnancy course, and newborn size at birth

All data was collected via an online questionnaire requesting information about maternal demographics (age, education, socio-economic and marital status, parity, and place of residence), pregnancy course (pregnancy complications including anemia, diabetes, hypertension, Rh incompatibility, medication), self-declared body height, and pre-pregnancy weight. After delivery, mothers were also asked to report delivery mode, child's sex, and infant characteristics at birth (gestational age, body mass, and length) from hospital health records.

Prenatal social support, depressive symptoms, and anxiety trait

Social support is operationalized on structural and functional dimensions [33]. While the structural dimension refers to how much a person is integrated into the social network (e.g., marital status, family members, friends), the functional dimension describes specific supportive functions the social relationships serve (e.g., emotional, instrumental, informational). This study utilized a functional approach by using Berliner Social Support Scales (BSSS) describing support perceived and received from others as well as personal needs and search for support [34,35]. The questionnaire consists of 6 subscales (Perceived, Actually Provided, and Received Social Support, Need for Support, Support Seeking, and Protective Buffering) that measure cognitive and behavioral aspects of social support. For the current analysis, only data about Perceived (PES) and Received Emotional Support (RES), each including four items, were considered. These forms of support were selected due to their highest expected effect on birth outcomes [36]. Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) [37,38] was used to assess prenatal maternal depressive symptoms. Although the scale was designed to determine the risk of postnatal depression, it was also successfully applied prenatally in previous studies [39]. Due to the longitudinal design of the Corona Mums project, we have decided to use this scale multiple times per participant, both pre- and postnatally. This scale contains ten items describing the participant's feelings during the last seven days. All items are rated on a 4-point scale. Higher scores indicate a higher risk of depression. The cut-off point to diagnose probable prenatal depression is 14 [39]. Maternal anxiety trait (STAI X2) was assessed using the State and Trait Anxiety Inventory [40,41] that includes 20 items describing a person's feelings. All items are rated on a 4-point scale (from "almost never" to "almost always"). Higher scores indicate greater anxiety.

Data on social support, depressive symptoms, and anxiety trait were collected prenatally upon entry to the study.

Statistical analysis

Maternal and infant characteristics were compared between groups of mothers with higher vs. lower levels of anxiety using a t-test when the data distribution approximated normal and a Chi² test when data were expressed as percent. These groups were formed based on the median value of the score from STAI X2.

Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) was used to assess the association between maternal psychological characteristics, e.g., STAI X2, EPDS, PES, RES, gestational age and infant size at birth.

The association between maternal STAI X2, PES and infant characteristics at birth adjusting for a range of already identified covariates was modeled using multiple regression. Separate models were produced for infant gestational age, birth weight, and length as dependent variables and maternal anxiety trait and social support as independent predictors, including maternal education, socio-economic status, child's sex, parity, complications during pregnancy, and maternal pre-pregnancy BMI as covariates.

Since the majority of women had higher education, data about education were dichotomized into lower (elementary or high school) and higher (college or university).

All analyses were conducted at the p-level established at 0.05 using open statistical software JAMOVI version 2.3.18 (2022).

Results

The mothers participating in the study were, on average, 31.0 years old ($SD=3.85$), had high education (85.8% with a university degree), and relatively high socio-economic status (Me of financial satisfaction=5; 72.7% with financial satisfaction score higher than 5). Fifty-six percent of the mothers were primiparous, and 40.6% of women delivered an infant following a vaginal, non-assisted childbirth. Fifty percent of women experienced some form of complications during pregnancy, and in 16.8%, an increased risk of prenatal depression was detected based on the results from EPDS.

Mothers with higher STAI X2 (Me ≥ 44) more frequently suffered from prenatal depressive symptoms ($\chi^2= 136$, $p<0.01$) and experienced complications during pregnancy more frequently ($\chi^2= 10.9$, $p<0.01$) when compared to women with lower STAI X2. They reported receiving less emotional support (RES) ($t=7.69$, $p<0.01$) and perceived lower emotional support (PES) ($t=8.88$, $p<0.01$).

Most infants were born with normal birth weight ($M=3476$ g, $SD=478.0$) and length ($M=54.9$ cm, $SD=2.78$). Less than 3% (2.8%) of newborns could be classified as small for gestational age with birth weight below 2500 g, while 11.8% were classified as large for gestational age with birth weight over 4000 g. Descriptive statistics for all mothers and infants participating in the study are presented in Table 1. Infants born to mothers with higher STAI X2

had higher birth length ($t=-2.13$, $p=0.03$) but did not differ significantly with their birth weight ($t=-1.44$, $p=0.15$).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and comparison between mothers with lower vs higher trait (STAI X2) of anxiety.

†-p for χ^2 test; STAI X2 – trait anxiety; PES – perceived emotional support; RES – received emotional support

	All women N=1080	Lower STAI X2 N=552	Higher STAI X2 N=528	p
Mothers				
Maternal age	31.0 (3.85)	31.1 (3.85)	30.8 (3.85)	0.13
Parity (primiparous%)	56.4	30.0	26.4	0.13†
Lower education (elementary or high school %)	6.2	3.1	3.1	0.83†
Financial satisfaction (low)	27.3	18.3	36.8	<0.01†
Postnatal depression (yes%)	16.8	1.9	14.8	<0.01†
STAI X2	44.3 (8.70)	37.6 (5.24)	51.4 (5.27)	<0.01
PES	13.7 (1.98)	14.2 (1.71)	13.2 (2.11)	<0.01
RES	31.6 (4.84)	32.7 (4.06)	30.5 (5.32)	<0.01
Pre-pregnancy BMI	24.0 (5.08)	23.8 (4.91)	24.3 (5.25)	0.08
Uncomplicated pregnancy (yes%)	49.4	27.8	21.6	<0.01†
Delivery mode (vaginal%)	40.6	21.0	19.6	0.78†
Infants				
Gestational age at birth	39.4 (1.31)	39.5 (1.34)	39.4 (1.28)	0.07
Pre-term (%)	7.7	3.2	4.5	0.57†
Sex (girls%)	47.5	25.1	22.4	0.31†
Birth weight (g)	3476.0 (478.0)	3456.0 (475.0)	3497.0 (480.0)	0.15
Birth length (cm)	54.9 (2.78)	54.7 (2.71)	55.1 (2.83)	0.03

Maternal STAI X2 score correlated positively with postnatal depressive symptoms ($\rho=0.73$, $p<0.01$) and negatively with PES ($\rho=-0.34$, $p<0.01$) and RES ($\rho=-0.34$, $p<0.01$). Depressive symptoms (as a continuous predictor) were negatively associated with PES ($\rho=-0.29$, $p<0.01$) and RES ($\rho=-0.26$, $p<0.01$). In contrast, no statistically significant association was found between depressive symptoms and newborn gestational age and size at birth. Similarly, although having an increased risk of depression (as a categorical predictor) was associated with lower PES ($U=64663$, $p<0.01$) and RES ($U=60121$, $p<0.01$) and higher STAI X2 ($U=21964$, $p<0.01$), no significant effects were found for newborn, gestational age and size at birth. Due to the high correlation between STAI X2 and depression, to avoid collinearity,

neither maternal risk of depression (as a categorical predictor) nor depressive symptoms (as a continuous predictor) were included in further analyses.

Gestational age at birth

Maternal PES, but not STAI X2 was positively associated with infant gestational age (GA) at birth. However, the association was on the verge of the significance level ($\beta=0.06$, $p=0.053$) after adjusting the model for the range of covariates (Table 2). The whole model was statistically significant ($F_{8,1070}=9.68$, $p<0.001$) and explained 7% of the variance in GA ($R^2_{adj}=0.07$), with pregnancy complications and primiparity (PA) as the most significant predictors ($\beta=0.41$, $p<0.001$ and $\beta=0.22$, $p<0.001$ respectively).

Table 2. Results of multiple regression models for gestational age at birth as a dependent variable. STAI X2 – trait anxiety; PES – perceived emotional support; significant associations bolded.

Predictor	Coeff	SE	-95%CI	+95%CI	t	p	β
Incept	39.25	0.46	38.37	40.14	86.84	<0.001	-
Pregnancy complications (no)	0.53	0.08	0.38	0.69	6.79	<0.001	0.41
Infant sex (boy)	-0.02	0.08	-0.17	0.13	-0.26	0.796	-0.02
Pre-pregnancy BMI	0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	-0.32	0.750	-0.01
Financial satisfaction (high)	-0.09	0.09	-0.27	0.09	-1.00	0.318	-0.07
Maternal education (higher)	-0.08	0.11	-0.29	0.14	-0.70	0.481	-0.06
Primiparity (no)	0.29	0.08	0.13	0.44	3.65	<0.001	0.22
STAI X2	-0.01	0.00	-0.02	0.00	-1.29	0.197	-0.04
PES	0.04	0.02	0.00	0.08	1.94	0.053	0.06

Birth weight

Maternal STAI X2 and PES were positively associated with infant birth weight ($\beta=0.07$, $p=0.014$ and $\beta=0.06$, $p=0.051$, respectively) after adjusting the model for a range of covariates (Table 3, Figure 1A). The whole model was statistically significant ($F_{8,1071}=40.9$, $p<0.001$) and explained about 23% of the variance in birthweight ($R^2_{adj}=0.23$), with GA and PA having the largest effect ($\beta=0.42$, $p<0.001$ and $\beta=-0.30$, $p<0.001$ for GA and PA, respectively).

Table 3. Results of multiple regression models for birth weight as a dependent variable.

STAI X2 – trait anxiety; PES – perceived emotional support; significant associations bolded.

Predictor	Coeff	SE	-95%CI	+95%CI	t	p	β
Incept	-3157.64	421.58	-3984.87	-2330.42	-7.49	<0.001	-
Pregnancy complications (no)	61.13	26.36	9.41	112.85	2.32	0.021	0.13
Infant sex (boy)	-127.77	25.66	-178.13	-77.42	-4.98	<0.001	-0.27
Pre-pregnancy BMI	8.14	2.55	3.14	13.14	3.19	0.001	0.09
Financial satisfaction (high)	35.08	29.83	-23.44	93.61	1.18	0.240	0.07
Gestational age	153.88	10.07	134.12	173.63	15.28	<0.001	0.42
Primiparity (no)	-143.62	26.26	-195.15	-92.10	-5.47	<0.001	-0.30
STAI X2	4.03	1.63	0.83	7.23	2.47	0.014	0.07
PES	13.68	7.00	-0.05	27.41	1.95	0.051	0.06

Figure 1. The association between the maternal trait anxiety and the predicted birth weight (A) and length (B); Estimated marginal means, adjusted for the means of other parameters in the models.

Birth length

The model showed that maternal STAI X2, but not PES was associated with the birth length of infants (Table 4, Figure 1B). Higher STAI X2 was associated with increased length at birth ($\beta=0.07$, $p=0.017$). The whole model was statistically significant ($F_{8,1069}=24.5$, $p<0.001$) and predicted about 15% of the variance in birth length ($R^2_{adj}=0.15$), with GA, infant sex and PA having the largest effect ($\beta=0.34$, $p<0.001$, $\beta=-0.24$, $p<0.001$ and $\beta=-0.22$, $p<0.001$ respectively).

Table 4. Results of multiple regression models for birth length as a dependent variable.

STAI X2 – trait anxiety; PES – perceived emotional support; significant associations bolded.

Predictor	Coeff	SE	-95%CI	+95%CI	t	p	β
Incept	24.02	2.58	18.97	29.08	9.32	<0.001	-
Pregnancy complications (no)	0.31	0.16	-0.01	0.62	1.91	0.056	0.11
Infant sex (boy)	-0.68	0.16	-0.99	-0.37	-4.33	<0.001	-0.24
Pre-pregnancy BMI	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.06	2.12	0.034	0.06
Financial satisfaction (high)	-0.10	0.18	-0.46	0.25	-0.57	0.567	-0.04
Gestational age	0.72	0.06	0.60	0.84	11.77	<0.001	0.34
Primiparity (no)	-0.60	0.16	-0.92	-0.29	-3.75	<0.001	-0.22
STAI X2	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.04	2.39	0.017	0.07
PES	0.04	0.04	-0.05	0.12	0.90	0.369	0.03

Discussion

This study investigated the effect of maternal anxiety and social support on the length of pregnancy and newborn size at birth during the COVID-19 pandemic. Following the evolutionary-based logic of the smoke detector principle and behavioral immune system, we found that a higher maternal anxiety trait was associated with higher weight and length at birth. Results of previous studies from pre-pandemic period depict slightly different associations. Hossein et al. [42] observed that higher anxiety trait during gestation predicted lower birth weight and shorter birth length, although the effect was only significant for severe anxiety. Other studies conducted in well-developed, non-pandemic settings suggested no effect of anxiety trait on infant birth outcomes [43–45]. Similarly, a study during the pandemic on 102 pregnant women from Iran found that maternal anxiety related to COVID-19 did not affect newborn birth weight or Apgar score [46].

Our results align with the behavioral immunity paradigm [14,15] and indicate that a higher maternal ability to detect threats in the unstable conditions of a pandemic was associated with better pregnancy outcomes. The results suggest that mothers with higher anxiety trait may have increased infant survival chances predicted by favorable birth parameters [47]. Conversely, infants born to mothers with lower anxiety trait, and decreased weight and length might experience a higher risk, especially in harsh or unpredictable environments. This highlights the association between maternal anxiety and reproductive success in challenging environmental conditions. Research by Jacobson and Roche's [48] suggested a similar effect, revealing that females with high anxiety trait experienced greater reproductive success in terms of offspring

across multiple generations. Women with high anxiety trait had more children, grandchildren, and great-grandchildren, suggesting a link between anxiety and increased reproductive success. Our results may thus offer an insight into the socio-biological mechanism underlying this association.

Several mechanisms might be proposed to explain the associations observed in our study. From the behavioral standpoint, COVID-19-related lockdown caused many changes in pregnant women's existence [24]. Positive changes in the behavior, especially in high-income countries, included experiencing less work-related stress, reduced exposure to infections, and better opportunities for nutritional support, exercise, rest and sleep [49]. Due to their lower threshold for threat detection, pregnant women with higher anxiety were more likely to adopt these lifestyle changes, which could lead to better birth outcomes for their newborns. Studies have shown that people with higher anxiety tended to increase their consumption of fresh fruits, vegetables, and dietary supplements during the pandemic [50,51]. Higher anxiety was also associated with greater social distancing [27,52], which could reduce the risk of infection for pregnant women. Additionally, higher anxiety during the lockdown was linked to lower physical activity, which could affect maternal energy balance and result in greater pregnancy weight gain and higher birth weight for the baby [53,54].

The proximate-level explanation of the observed association is based on the observation that higher anxiety trait is associated with a blunted cortisol awakening response (CAR) and lower baseline awakening cortisol levels, which might be interpreted as a sign of deregulated activity of the HPA axis [55,56]. Although it has to be noted that anxiety state under non-threatening environmental conditions is frequently associated with higher pregnancy cortisol levels [57,58] and fewer studies have concentrated on trait than on state anxiety during pregnancy, indeed, individuals with high anxiety trait have lower levels of adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH) and cortisol, as well as lower activation of epinephrine and norepinephrine secretion during psychosocial stress in non-pregnant [59] and pregnant [60] individuals and less variable cortisol response (CAR) [61]. This may suggest that pregnant mothers with high anxiety trait could produce lower levels of cortisol during stressful periods of the COVID-19 pandemic. Interestingly, lower maternal CAR and cortisol levels during the day were also associated with higher infant size at birth and a lower risk of being born small for gestational age (SGA) [62]. These results may further underlie the relative costs of higher anxiety for mothers and the benefits of this trait for infant birth size under threatening environmental conditions.

It's crucial to understand that the same mechanisms may benefit offspring survival in uncertain and threatening environments and hinder it during stable periods later in life. Before the pandemic, high maternal anxiety was linked to lower birth weight and an increased risk of giving birth to an SGA infant [42,63]. Additionally, high maternal metabolic energy availability, reduced physical activity, and greater weight gain during pregnancy were associated with adverse outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, obesity, diabetes, and other metabolic complications later in life [64]. All these effects could be considered the costs of the *false alarms* of the oversensitive *smoke detector*. The heightened anxiety trait may not be adaptive during times of environmental stability, but such times were relatively rare in our evolutionary past, characterized by unpredictable access to energy resources and higher exposure to pathogens. Therefore, the observed negative effects of increased maternal anxiety trait likely represent a mismatch between our evolutionary past and current environmental conditions.

Although increased maternal anxiety trait during the pandemic may benefit infant survival, it may also impose psychological and physiological costs on the mother. It was demonstrated that individuals with high anxiety trait are more vulnerable to negative consequences of stress, including an increased risk of stress-induced depression [65]. Moreover, mothers with high anxiety trait were more prone to developing antepartum and postpartum depression [66]. We also found the same effect in our study. Based on the results from the EPDS scale, 17% of women with high anxiety trait and only 2% of women with low anxiety trait could suffer from perinatal depression. Mothers with high anxiety trait suffered from more pregnancy complications, as also indicated by the results of our study. This may suggest that increased chances for higher maternal reproductive success may come with the costs to her own health and survival.

Our research shows that mothers with strong emotional support tend to have infants with higher birth weights. This result corroborates previous studies that found a similar link between social support and birth weight. For instance, a study conducted in India, Peru, and Vietnam showed that participation in women's support groups during pregnancy was associated with higher infant birth weight [31]. Earlier studies also demonstrated the beneficial effect of support for mothers and families on the risk of giving birth to SGA infants [67] and fetal growth [30]. Interestingly, we found no association of PES with birth length. The physiological mechanisms of how maternal social support is translated into prenatal growth and development are unclear [68]. On a related note, it is possible that different maternal mental characteristics influence birth

length and weight. Our results confirm this notion by the lack of a significant effect of PES on birth length and a significant one on birth weight.

Numerous benefits of social support for pregnant mothers include a decrease in risk of perinatal depression and buffering against the adverse effects of psychosocial stress and anxiety [69]. On the other hand, social isolation (limited social support) has been shown to increase cortisol awakening responses and cortisol levels over the day in both men and women [70]. As previously mentioned, higher cortisol responsiveness during pregnancy is associated with worse birth outcomes [61,62]. Furthermore, studies have demonstrated a positive effect of social support on individual health status and reproductive function independently from perceived stress [33]. For instance, maternal social support from family and friends may affect pregnancy via adherence to nutrition guidelines and prenatal care [71]. Finally, high perceived emotional social support, regardless of anxiety or psychosocial stress, predicted improved immune functions in breastfeeding mothers [29]. These results point to the possible multiple foundations of the positive effect of social support on the birth outcome, also demonstrated in our study.

The paramount strength of our study lies in the substantial number of participants and the longitudinal design, enabling us to track participants from pregnancy to post-birth. The homogeneity of our sample, comprising women with high education and socioeconomic status, allowed to effectively avoid confounding factors related to birth outcomes [72,73]. As for the limitations, the large number of participants followed during the COVID-19 pandemic dictated online surveying to collect data about maternal and infant anthropometrics and lifestyle factors. This forced us to rely solely on self-declared information. To decrease the error whenever possible, we asked for confirmation of the declared data with medical documentation such as the child's health and pregnancy records.

In summary, our data suggests that higher anxiety in pregnant mothers may lead to better pregnancy outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. This aligns with the logic of *smoke detector principle*, indicating the adaptive nature of anxiety in threatening environments. Although, as we have shown in this study, in such conditions, maternal anxiety trait might be beneficial in the context of immediate infant survival, in a more stable environment, mothers and infants could pay a cost of it in the form of increased risk of perinatal depression and metabolic diseases later during life. Our study also supports the positive effect of emotional and social support on birth outcomes.

Ethics:

The study protocol was approved by the Bioethics Committee of Jagiellonian University (decision number: 1072.6120.359.2020).

Data availability:

The data associated with this research are available at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16263884>.

Authors contribution:

A.A., D.P.D., M.K., U.M.M., M.M., and A.Z conceived and designed the research. A.A. and A.C. collected the data. A.Z and D.P.D. performed statistical analysis. A.Z. prepared the first draft of the manuscript. U.M.M. secured funding for the research. All authors have read, contributed to, and approved the final version of the paper.

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References:

1. Davis EP, Narayan AJ. Pregnancy as a period of risk, adaptation, and resilience for mothers and infants. *Dev Psychopathol* 2020;**32**:1625–39.
2. Staneva A, Bogossian F, Pritchard M *et al*. The effects of maternal depression, anxiety, and perceived stress during pregnancy on preterm birth: A systematic review. *Women Birth J Aust Coll Midwives* 2015;**28**:179–93.
3. Grigoriadis S, Graves L, Peer M *et al*. Maternal Anxiety During Pregnancy and the Association With Adverse Perinatal Outcomes: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Clin Psychiatry* 2018;**79**:17r12011.
4. Field T. Postnatal anxiety prevalence, predictors and effects on development: A narrative review. *Infant Behav Dev* 2018;**51**:24–32.
5. Shahhosseini Z, Pourasghar M, Khalilian A *et al*. A Review of the Effects of Anxiety During Pregnancy on Children’s Health. *Mater Socio-Medica* 2015;**27**:200–2.

6. Rees S, Channon S, Waters CS. The impact of maternal prenatal and postnatal anxiety on children's emotional problems: a systematic review. *Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 2019;**28**:257–80.
7. Raina J, El-Messidi A, Badeghiesh A *et al*. Pregnancy hypertension and its association with maternal anxiety and mood disorders: A population-based study of 9 million pregnancies. *J Affect Disord* 2021;**281**:533–8.
8. OuYang H, Chen B, Abdulrahman A-M *et al*. Associations between Gestational Diabetes and Anxiety or Depression: A Systematic Review. *J Diabetes Res* 2021;**2021**:9959779.
9. McNamara J, Townsend ML, Herbert JS. A systemic review of maternal wellbeing and its relationship with maternal fetal attachment and early postpartum bonding. *PLOS ONE* 2019;**14**:e0220032.
10. Bateson M, Brilot B, Nettle D. Anxiety: An Evolutionary Approach. *Can J Psychiatry* 2011;**56**:707–15.
11. Nesse RM. Natural selection and the regulation of defenses: A signal detection analysis of the smoke detector principle. *Evol Hum Behav* 2005;**26**:88–105.
12. Nesse RM. The smoke detector principle: Signal detection and optimal defense regulation. *Evol Med Public Health* 2019;**2019**:1.
13. Elwood LS, Wolitzky-Taylor K, Olatunji BO. Measurement of anxious traits: a contemporary review and synthesis. *Anxiety Stress Coping* 2012;**25**:647–66.
14. Nesse RM. The Smoke Detector Principle. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 2006;**935**:75–85.
15. Schaller M, Park JH. The Behavioral Immune System (and Why It Matters). *Curr Dir Psychol Sci* 2011;**20**:99–103.
16. Kim SY, Yeniova AÖ. Global, regional, and national incidence and mortality of COVID-19 in 237 countries and territories, January 2022: a systematic analysis for World Health Organization COVID-19 Dashboard. *Life Cycle* 2022;**2**, DOI: 10.54724/lc.2022.e10.
17. Shang W, Wang Y, Yuan J *et al*. Global Excess Mortality during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Vaccines* 2022;**10**:1702.
18. Wieckiewicz M, Danel D, Pondel M *et al*. Identification of risk groups for mental disorders, headache and oral behaviors in adults during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Sci Rep* 2021;**11**:10964.
19. Arzamani N, Soraya S, Hadi F *et al*. The COVID-19 pandemic and mental health in pregnant women: A review article. *Front Psychiatry* 2022;**13**.
20. Stepowicz A, Wencka B, Bieńkiewicz J *et al*. Stress and Anxiety Levels in Pregnant and Post-Partum Women during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2020;**17**:9450.
21. Sun S, Savitz DA, Wellenius GA. Changes in Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes Associated With the COVID-19 Pandemic in the United States. *JAMA Netw Open* 2021;**4**:e2129560.

22. Wen J. Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on birth outcomes: A retrospective cohort study in Nanjing, China. *Front Public Health* 2022;**10**.
23. Kirchengast S, Hartmann B. Pregnancy Outcome during the First COVID 19 Lockdown in Vienna, Austria. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2021;**18**:3782.
24. Yao XD, Li Y, Jiang H *et al*. COVID-19 pandemic and neonatal birth weight: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Public Health* 2023;**220**:10–7.
25. Oakley A. *Social Support and Motherhood (Reissue): The Natural History of a Research Project*. Policy Press, 2018.
26. Balaji AB, Claussen AH, Smith DC *et al*. Social Support Networks and Maternal Mental Health and Well-Being. *J Womens Health* 2007;**16**:1386–96.
27. Ciochoń A, Apanasewicz A, Danel DP *et al*. Antenatal Classes in the Context of Prenatal Anxiety and Depression during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2022;**19**:5073.
28. Żyrek J, Klimek M, Apanasewicz A *et al*. Social support during pregnancy and the risk of postpartum depression in Polish women: A prospective study. *Sci Rep* 2024;**14**:6906.
29. Ziomkiewicz A, Apanasewicz A, Danel DP *et al*. Maternal Distress and Social Support Are Linked to Human Milk Immune Properties. *Nutrients* 2021;**13**:1857.
30. Feldman PJ, Dunkel-Schetter C, Sandman CA *et al*. Maternal Social Support Predicts Birth Weight and Fetal Growth in Human Pregnancy. *Psychosom Med* 2000;**62**:715.
31. Lee H-Y, Oh J, Perkins JM *et al*. Associations between maternal social capital and infant birth weight in three developing countries: a cross-sectional multilevel analysis of Young Lives data. *BMJ Open* 2019;**9**:e024769.
32. Wado YD, Afework MF, Hindin MJ. Effects of Maternal Pregnancy Intention, Depressive Symptoms and Social Support on Risk of Low Birth Weight: A Prospective Study from Southwestern Ethiopia. *PLOS ONE* 2014;**9**:e96304.
33. Uchino BN, Bowen K, de Grey RK *et al*. Social support and physical health: Models, mechanisms, and opportunities. *Principles and Concepts of Behavioral Medicine: A Global Handbook*. Springer New York, 2018, 341–72.
34. Łuszczynska A, Kowalska M, Mazurkiewicz M *et al*. Berlińskie Skale Wsparcia Społecznego (BSSS) : wyniki wstępnych badań nad akceptacją skal i ich własnościami psychometrycznymi. *Stud Psychol* 2006;**44**:17–27.
35. Schulz U, Schwarzer R. Soziale Unterstützung bei der Krankheitsbewältigung: Die Berliner Social Support Skalen (BSSS). [Social Support in Coping with Illness: The Berlin Social Support Scales (BSSS)]. *Diagnostica* 2003;**49**:73–82.
36. Al-Mutawtah M, Campbell E, Kubis H-P *et al*. Women's experiences of social support during pregnancy: a qualitative systematic review. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2023;**23**:782.

37. Cox JL, Holden JM, Sagovsky R. Detection of postnatal depression. Development of the 10-item Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale. *Br J Psychiatry J Ment Sci* 1987;**150**:782–6.
38. Kossakowska K. Edynburska Skala Depresji Poporodowej – właściwości psychometryczne i charakterystyka. *Acta Univ Lodz Folia Psychol* 2013:39–50.
39. Gibson J, McKenzie-McHarg K, Shakespeare J *et al.* A systematic review of studies validating the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale in antepartum and postpartum women. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 2009;**119**:350–64.
40. Spielberger CD, Gorsuch RL. *Manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory.*, 1983.
41. Sosnowski T, Wrześniewski K, Jaworowska A *et al.* *STAI - Inwentarz Stanu i Cechy Lęku STAI.* Warszawa: Pracownia Testów Psychologicznych, 2011.
42. Hosseini SM, Biglan MW, Larkby C *et al.* Trait anxiety in pregnant women predicts offspring birth outcomes. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol* 2009;**23**:557–66.
43. Bödecs T, Horváth B, Szilágyi E *et al.* Effects of depression, anxiety, self-esteem, and health behaviour on neonatal outcomes in a population-based Hungarian sample. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2011;**154**:45–50.
44. Engel SM, Berkowitz GS, Wolff MS *et al.* Psychological trauma associated with the World Trade Center attacks and its effect on pregnancy outcome. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol* 2005;**19**:334–41.
45. Sjöström K, Valentin L, Thelin T *et al.* Maternal anxiety in late pregnancy and fetal hemodynamics. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 1997;**74**:149–55.
46. Mirzaie F, Rezaie Keikhaie K, Badakhsh M *et al.* Evaluation of Coronavirus Anxiety in Pregnant Women on Apgar Score and Birth Weight After One Year of Coronavirus Outbreak (Case Study: Zabol, Iran). *J Obstet Gynecol Cancer Res* 2021;**7**:89–98.
47. Wilcox AJ. On the importance—and the unimportance— of birthweight. *Int J Epidemiol* 2001;**30**:1233–41.
48. Jacobson NC, Roche MJ. Current evolutionary adaptiveness of anxiety: Extreme phenotypes of anxiety predict increased fertility across multiple generations. *J Psychiatr Res* 2018;**106**:82–90.
49. Stampini V, Monzani A, Caristia S *et al.* The perception of Italian pregnant women and new mothers about their psychological wellbeing, lifestyle, delivery, and neonatal management experience during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown: a web-based survey. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2021;**21**:473.
50. Doğan G, Özyildirim C, Yabancı Ayhan N. Supplementation use and diet changes during COVID-19 pandemic according to anxiety level and Mediterranean diet adherence. *Clin Nutr ESPEN* 2023;**54**:122–9.
51. Górnicka M, Drywień ME, Zielinska MA *et al.* Dietary and Lifestyle Changes During COVID-19 and the Subsequent Lockdowns among Polish Adults: A Cross-Sectional Online Survey PLifeCOVID-19 Study. *Nutrients* 2020;**12**:2324.

52. Salali GD, Uysal MS, Bevan A. Adaptive function and correlates of anxiety during a pandemic. *Evol Med Public Health* 2021;**9**:393–405.
53. Frontini R, Rebelo-Gonçalves R, Amaro N *et al.* The Relationship Between Anxiety Levels, Sleep, and Physical Activity During COVID-19 Lockdown: An Exploratory Study. *Front Psychol* 2021;**12**.
54. Nethery E, Hutcheon JA, Kotaska A *et al.* Weight gain in pregnancy and infant birthweight after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic: an interrupted time series analysis. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2023;**117**:364–72.
55. Gao H, Liu X, Gou L *et al.* High Trait Anxiety Predicts Decreased Cortisol Awakening Response. *J Psychopathol Behav Assess* 2023, DOI: 10.1007/s10862-023-10045-9.
56. Pluess M, Bolten M, Pirke K-M *et al.* Maternal trait anxiety, emotional distress, and salivary cortisol in pregnancy. *Biol Psychol* 2010;**83**:169–75.
57. Kane HS, Dunkel Schetter C, Glynn LM, Hobel CJ, Sandman CA. Pregnancy anxiety and prenatal cortisol trajectories. *Biol Psychol*. 2014;**100**:13-19.
58. Leff-Gelman P, Flores-Ramos M, Carrasco AEÁ, *et al.* Cortisol and DHEA-S levels in pregnant women with severe anxiety. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2020;**20**(1):393.
59. Jezova D, Makatsori A, Duncko R *et al.* High trait anxiety in healthy subjects is associated with low neuroendocrine activity during psychosocial stress. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry* 2004;**28**:1331–6.
60. Walker S, O'Connor DB, Schaefer A *et al.* The cortisol awakening response: Associations with trait anxiety and stress reactivity. *Personal Individ Differ* 2011;**51**:123–7.
61. Ross KM, Mander H, Rinne G *et al.* Pregnancy-specific anxiety and gestational length: The mediating role of diurnal cortisol indices. *Psychoneuroendocrinology* 2023;**153**:106114.
62. Vlenterie R, Prins JB, Roeleveld N *et al.* Associations between maternal awakening salivary cortisol levels in mid-pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes. *Arch Gynecol Obstet* 2022;**306**:1989–99.
63. Ding X-X, Wu Y-L, Xu S-J *et al.* Maternal anxiety during pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. *J Affect Disord* 2014;**159**:103–10.
64. Leonard SA, Panelli DM. Quasi-experimental study designs can inform pandemic effects on nutrition and weight gain in pregnancy. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2023;**117**:216–7.
65. Weger M, Sandi C. High anxiety trait: A vulnerable phenotype for stress-induced depression. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev* 2018;**87**:27–37.
66. Hamed SA, Elwasify M, Abdelhafez M *et al.* Peripartum depression and its predictors: A longitudinal observational hospital-based study. *World J Psychiatry* 2022;**12**:1061–75.
67. Pryor J, Thompson J, Robinson E *et al.* Stress and lack of social support as risk factors for small-for-gestational-age birth. *Acta Paediatr* 2003;**92**:62–4.

68. Snell-Rood E, Snell-Rood C. The developmental support hypothesis: adaptive plasticity in neural development in response to cues of social support. *Philos Trans R Soc B Biol Sci* 2020;**375**:20190491.
69. Bedaso A, Adams J, Peng W *et al.* The relationship between social support and mental health problems during pregnancy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Reprod Health* 2021;**18**:162.
70. Grant N, Hamer M, Steptoe A. Social Isolation and Stress-related Cardiovascular, Lipid, and Cortisol Responses. *Ann Behav Med* 2009;**37**:29–37.
71. Liu Y, Guo N, Feng H *et al.* The prevalence of trimester-specific dietary supplements and associated factors during pregnancy: An observational study. *Front Pharmacol* 2023;**14**.
72. Caut C, Leach M, Steel A. Dietary guideline adherence during preconception and pregnancy: A systematic review. *Matern Child Nutr* 2020;**16**:e12916.
73. de Wolff MG, Backhausen MG, Iversen ML *et al.* Prevalence and predictors of maternal smoking prior to and during pregnancy in a regional Danish population: a cross-sectional study. *Reprod Health* 2019;**16**:82.